

DEVELOPMENT OF DRILLING TECHNOLOGY WITH HYDRAULIC MOTORS IN SALT BLOOD CONDITIONS.

R.S. Shaymanova, M.K. Urazov, D.N. Yuldosheva
Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology
NX Shaymanova 15th general education school teacher

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Abstract: Improving the efficiency of deep wells and fairways in oilfields with salt rock deposits by developing and implementing drilling techniques and technologies through hydraulic drilling motors (HDM).

The results of studies on the performance of drill bits and the energy characteristics of various types of hydraulic well motors are presented. Studies bench and the field conditions analytical and experimental of methods used without done increased _

VNIIBT-BI LLC by work type SDI output hydraulic the engine test transfer for certified on the benches series and experimental hydraulic with a well of engines energy characteristics advantages comparative evaluation in order to machine tool studies was conducted .drilling enterprises :

- SOI-250 (with a diameter of 76-127 mm PDM test while transferring);
- SOI-500 (PDM with a diameter of 195-240 mm and turbodrills test in transfer).

Test on the machines 2D-76 screw obtained with a well engine and TVM-195 turbodrill energy features examples in the form shown . 1.

Straight away drilling on the machines scientific research their work take to go in the process certified AMT-100 drill management from the station used without , mechanic logging works take went and drilling of the process parameters note done _ Experimental the field studies optimal drilling in the process mode in determining " stopped drum " method applied , this reliable and time spending according to the most advanced technological is considered Method the well the bottom work on the way out bit axial load change speed constant respectively from setting consists of Optimal drilling mode choose change speed maximum has been axial load value from detection consists of is , it is given in between the most high to ROP suitable will come

Rice. Figure 1. Bench characteristics of the main engine obtained on test stands: a) 2D-76 screw engine with a diameter of 76 mm (SOI-250 bench); b) TVM-195 turbodrill (SOI-500) with a diameter of 195 mm.

As a result of studying the performance of different sized drill bits and hydraulic motors in drilling wells and roads, the effective parameters of the drilling mode were determined and specific technical and technological recommendations were developed for their use.

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